

1 **Fructo-oligosaccharides in table grapes and response to storage**

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Abstract

26 Fructo-oligosaccharides (FOS) have been recognized as health food ingredients with a protective
27 effect against environmental stresses in plants. We have analysed the profiles of individual FOS
28 in Cardinal table grape pulp, until now undetected, and quantified their changes in response to
29 low temperature and high CO₂ levels. FOS separation and quantification was carried out using
30 anion-exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD), and the
31 glucose, fructose and sucrose content of the grapes was also determined. Five FOS were
32 identified and quantified: 1-kestose, neokestose, nystose, nystose b and kestopentaose. While in
33 non-treated table grapes the endogenous FOS remained at steady state levels during storage at 0
34 °C, exposure to 20% CO₂ for 3 days significant increases the levels of 1-kestose and
35 kestopentaose, members of the inulin series. Considering the competitive advantage afforded by
36 CO₂-treated grapes, this transitory FOS accumulation could provide protection against damage
37 caused by low temperature storage.

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40 Keywords: Fructo-oligosaccharides, low temperature, carbon dioxide, carbohydrate,

41 *Vitis vinifera*.

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51 1. Introduction

52 Due to the fact that chemical treatment to control fruit quality and diseases are
53 potentially harmful to humans it has been necessary to develop effective, harmless and
54 protective physical treatments. Treatments with low temperature and high CO₂
55 treatments are widely used to improve storage life and the quality of different kinds of
56 fruit (Kader, 1986). Table grapes are not susceptible to injury at temperatures above
57 freezing, although studies on Cardinal grapes indicated that they are sensitive to a
58 temperature shift to 0 °C. In this regard, altered anthocyanidin profiles and activation of
59 stress-induced gene expression have been noted in grapes stored at 0 °C (Romero,
60 Sanchez-Ballesta, Maldonado, Escribano & Merodio, 2008). However, such changes
61 were less noticeable in berries that had been treated at high CO₂ concentrations.
62 Moreover, treatment with 20% CO₂ for 3 days was effective in improving the
63 appearance and quality of the berries (Sanchez-Ballesta et al., 2006). In other table
64 grape varieties, high CO₂ concentrations also successfully maintain berry quality,
65 reducing stem browning, retarding decay and thereby prolonging their storage life
66 (Martínez-Romero, Guillén, Castillo, Valero & Serrano, 2003; Yahia, Nelson & Kader,
67 1983).

68 In grapes, glucose and fructose account for at least 99% of the carbohydrates,
69 constituting a large proportion of the total soluble solids. Sucrose is also present in
70 small amounts, its levels varying in function of the species and varieties (Huai-Feng,
71 Ben-Hong, Pei-Ge, Shao-Hua & Lian-Sheng, 2006; Winkler, Cook, Kliewer & Lider,
72 1974). Several pathways that link the synthesis and breakdown of carbohydrate reserves
73 are in dynamic equilibrium, and they are critical in determining fruit quality during
74 storage. Altering the pattern of soluble sugars, particularly the production of high
75 relative levels of sucrose, is often associated with increased cold hardiness in a wide

76 range of plant species (Gibson, 2005). Fructans are polydisperse water-soluble fructose
77 based polymers that result from extended sucrose metabolism (Weyens et al., 2004). In
78 plants, they may have functions other than carbon storage, and for many years they have
79 been implicated in abiotic stress-tolerance (Livingston, Hinch and Heyer, 2009).

80 Heterogeneous mixtures of fructans with different degrees of polymerization (DP) and
81 structures are usually present in plants. The type of fructans found in plants (either
82 oligomeric or polymeric molecules) and the specific fructans found are species-
83 dependent, and they are strongly influenced by environmental conditions and the stage
84 of plant developmental (Sims, 2003). Fructan accumulation during periods of reduced
85 growth associated with non-freezing low temperature has frequently been correlated
86 with increased freezing tolerance (Eagles, 1967; Pontis, 1989). Although this
87 phenomenon appears to be relatively common, there is no data available on fructan
88 distribution and concentration variations in fruit stored under different environmental
89 conditions.

90 Fructans are a series of homologous oligo and polysaccharides in which fructosyl units
91 (F) are bound by β linkage to sucrose (GF). The basic fructan trisaccharides, 1-kestose
92 (1^F - β -D-fructosylsucrose) and neokestose (6^G - β -D-fructosylsucrose), are produced by
93 linking a fructose moiety to one of the three primary hydroxyl groups of sucrose. Their
94 synthesis reportedly begins in the vacuole with sucrose as both the donor and substrate.

95 The first transferase enzyme, sucrose:sucrose 1-fructosyltransferase (1-SST), forms 1-
96 kestose from two sucrose molecules (releasing glucose). Subsequently, an elongating
97 enzyme, fructan:fructan 1-fructosyltransferase (1-FFT), transfers a single terminal
98 fructose residue from an oligosaccharide to the same carbon position on another
99 molecule, thereby producing the fructan inulin (Edelman & Jefford, 1968; Valluru &
100 Van den Ende, 2008).

101 Currently, fructans are being investigated as functional food ingredients and they have
102 been shown to be effective against chronic inflammatory bowel disease. Inulin-type
103 fructans possess mainly β -(2-1) linkages that escape from the action of human digestive
104 enzymes and therefore, they reach the large intestine unchanged and serve as
105 fermentative substrates for the colon microflora (Cummings, Macfarlane & Englyst,
106 2001). Furthermore, fructans with only a small DP have a sweet taste and their energetic
107 value is theoretically lower than that of sucrose. By contrast, large DP fructans form
108 emulsions with a fat-like texture and neutral taste. In the food industry, there is much
109 interest in using these fructans as low-calories food ingredients and as nutraceutical
110 ingredients (Vijn & Smeekens, 1999).

111 The objective of the present study was to analyze the profile of individual FOS in table
112 grapes, a non-fructan-accumulating plant, and to define their changes in response to low
113 temperature and high CO₂ exposure. This information is essential to determine whether
114 the stress/tolerance response can be monitored by the changes in fructo-oligosaccharide
115 accumulation and by extension, to evaluate whether such high CO₂ treatment (20% for
116 3 days) is efficient in maintaining grape quality during storage at 0 °C.

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119 **2. Materials and methods**

120 **2.1 Plant material**

121 Early-harvested bunches of table grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L. cv. ‘Cardinal’) from Camas
122 (Sevilla, Spain) were pre-cooled in forced-air for 14 h at -1 °C and then stored at 0 °C
123 (± 0.5) with 95% relative humidity in two sealed 1 m³ neoprene containers. Ten plastic
124 boxes containing about 3 kg of table grapes per box were stored in each container in the
125 dark. One lot was stored in air for 22 days (non-treated fruit) and the other was

126 maintained under a gas mixture containing 20% CO₂+20% O₂+60% N₂ (CO₂-treated
127 fruit) for 3 days. The CO₂ concentration was maintained throughout the pretreatment
128 period and measured daily using an automated gas chromatography system equipped
129 with a thermal conductivity detector and Poraplot Q column (Varian Chrompack
130 CP20033P). After 3 days, these CO₂-treated grapes were transferred to air until the end
131 of the 22-day storage period. Initially and at each storage time (3, 6, 12 and 22 days) ten
132 clusters were sampled, five were CO₂-treated and the remaining five non-treated. A total
133 of 90 berries were taken for analysis, 45 berries were used for to analyze their quality as
134 described elsewhere (Sanchez-Ballesta et al., 2006), and the remainder were peeled, the
135135 seeds removed and then frozen at -80 °C.

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137 2.2 Extraction and chromatographic determination of glucose, fructose and 138 sucrose

139 Approximately 1 g of each sample was homogenized in 5 ml of ultra-pure water and
140 centrifuged at 30,000g for 20 min, after which the supernatants were filtered through a
141 0.45 µm pore size membrane. Glucose, fructose and sucrose were analyzed by HPLC
142 using a refractive index (RI) detector (Smartline 2300, Knauer) and a CARBOSep-
143 Coregel 87 N (7.8 × 300mm) column. The eluate was sterilized with ultra-pure water
144 and it was analyzed at an elution rate of 0.6 ml/min and at an oven temperature of 85 °C.
145 Appropriate dilutions of a solution containing glucose, fructose and sucrose (Sigma,
146 Steinheim, Germany) were used as calibration standards. Chromatographic peaks were
147 identified by comparing sample retention times with those of known standard mixtures
148 and the data was acquired using DataApex Clarity software. The content of each sugar
149 was expressed as mg/g fresh weight (FW) of sample and the data were the means of the
150 three replicates and two different measurements were made.

151 **2.3 Extraction of FOS**

152 To obtain an enriched FOS fraction, prior extraction of grape pulp was required.
153 Accordingly, 3 g of pulp was homogenised in 10 ml of 85% ethanol and the mixture
154 was boiled under reflux in a water bath for 5 min. After centrifugation at 5,000g for 20
155 min at 4 °C, the supernatant was decanted and evaporated to dryness under vacuum at
156 40 °C, and it was then redissolved with 10 ml of deionised water. Two aliquots of 1.4 ml
157 were filtered through a 0.22 µm filters and analysed by high-performance anion-
158 exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD) to
159 determinate the nystose [**4b**: 6^G (1-β-D-fructosyl)₂ sucrose; **4c**: 1^F,6^G-di-β-D-fructosyl
160 sucrose] and kestopentaose [**5a**: 1^F-(1-β-D-fructosyl)₃ sucrose] content.
161 Due to the high levels of reducing sugars and sucrose in the pulp of table grape,
162 quantification of 1-kestose **3a**: 1^F-(1-β-D-fructosyl)sucrose) and neokestose **3b**: 6^G-β-D-
163 fructosylsucrose required pre-treatment with an activated carbon Darco G60, 100 mesh
164 (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany). Thus, the remaining 7.2 ml of supernatant was stirred
165 with 1.2 g of activated carbon for 45 min at room temperature to remove the mono- and
166 disaccharides. After centrifugation at 5,000g for 20 min, the pellet was dissolved in 7.2
167 ml of deionised water and stirred for 1 min. The pellet was again recovered by
168 centrifugation at 5,000g for 20 min, it was dissolved in 7 ml of 95% ethanol and stirred
169 for 45 min at room temperature. After a further centrifugation at 5,000g, the supernatant
170 was vacuum evaporated to dryness at 40 °C and then redissolved in 10 ml of deionised
171 water, filtered through 0.22 µm pore membranes and analysed by HPAEC-PAD to
172 determine the 1-kestose and neokestose content.

173 **2.4 Chromatographic determination of FOS**

174 The determination of FOS was carried out by HPAEC-PAD, equipped with a CarboPac
175 PA1 carbohydrate column. Samples were analysed on an Ion Chromatography 817

176 Bioscan (Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland) system equipped with a pulsed amperometric
177 detector (PAD) and a gold electrode. A three-step PAD protocol was used with the
178 following time intervals (ms) and potentials (mV): t1, 400/E1 = +0.05 (detection); t2,
179 200/E2 = +0.75 (cleaning); t3, 400/E3 = -0.15 (regeneration). Gradient elution was
180 carried out by combining eluents A (150 mM NaOH) and B (500 mM acetate-Na in 150
181 mM NaOH) as follows: 0-1 min 100% A; 1-2 min 95-90% A; 2-20 min 90-60% A; 20-
182 22 60-0% A; 30-35 min 0-95%; 35-40 min 95-100%. Samples (1.5 ml) were injected
183 using an autosampler (model, 838 Advanced Sample Processor, Metrohm, Herisau,
184 Switzerland) and the flow rate through the column was 1 ml/min, leading to a sampling
185 time (t_s) of 40 min.

186 Identification of FOS was performed by comparison with the retention time of authentic
187 standard mixtures (1-kestose and nystose from Sigma, Steinheim, Germany, and
188 kestopentaose from Megazyme, Co.Wicklow, Ireland), and with those reported in the
189 literature when using the same chromatographic method (Cardelle-Cobas, Costo,
190 Corzo & Villamiel, 2009). The FOS content was expressed as $\mu\text{g/g}$ FW of sample and
191 the data were the mean of the three replicates and two different measurements were
192 carried out.

193 **2.5 Statistical analysis**

194 One-or two-way ANOVA and correlational analyses were employed using SPSS ver.
195 19.0. The multicomparison of means was assessed by Bonferroni's test, to determine the
196 level of significance at $p < 0.05$. The main effects of CO₂ treatment, time of storage, and
197197 treatment x time interaction on table grapes were analysed.

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200 **3. Results and discussion**

201 In this study, the glucose, fructose and sucrose content in the pulp of non-treated and
202 CO₂-treated table grapes during storage at 0 °C was determined (Table 1). There was a
203 clear predominance of reducing sugars over sucrose in berries in both non-treated and
204 CO₂-treated grapes. Statistical analysis confirmed that the factor ‘CO₂-time interaction’
205 influenced the amounts of all the sugars detected. However, in terms of the effects of
206 the different factors analysed (CO₂ treatment, time and the CO₂-time interaction),
207 ANOVA confirmed that while the factor ‘time’ significantly affected the glucose,
208 fructose and sucrose content ($p < 0.05$), the ‘CO₂ treatment’ factor only significantly
209 affected the sucrose content. Specifically, at the end of CO₂ treatment, the levels of
210 sucrose declined, reaching values significantly lower than those observed for non-
211 treated fruit by day 3 at 0 °C.

212 When transferred to air lower sucrose levels were recorded in CO₂-treated grapes
213 throughout the storage period, except for a transient increase on day 12. These results,
214 suggest that the sucrose demand for both structural and non-structural carbohydrates
215 increases in CO₂-treated fruit during storage at 0 °C, thus explaining the lower levels of
216 sucrose than those quantified in non-treated berries. On the contrary, the high levels of
217 sucrose in non-treated fruit stored at 0 °C suggest that they suffer some kind of
218 restriction or reduced demand for carbon skeletons. In this sense, large quantities of
219 cytosolic photosynthates have been reported at low temperatures (Pollock & Cairns,
220 1991). A relationship between the levels of sucrose and FOS has already been observed
221 (Darbyshire & Henry, 1981), suggesting that sucrose may control the ability of plants to
222 synthesize fructans. Hence, it was proposed that the degree of polymerization might be
223 related to the total concentration of non-structural carbohydrates (Jaime et al., 2000).
224 HPAEC-PAD analysis identified five FOS: 1-kestose (**3a**), neokestose (**3b**), nystose
225 (**4c**) nystose b (**4b**) and kestopentaose (**5a**) in table grapes (Fig. 1). The figure shows the

226 HPAEC-PAD chromatograms of different FOS extracted from pulp berries with (A) and
227 without (B) activated carbon pre-treatment. In order to further verify the presence of
228 FOS, the same sample (A₁) was spiked with the 1-kestose (**3a**) (A₂) standard, and the
229 corresponding (B₁) sample was spiked with the nystose (**4c**) and kestopentaose (**5a**) (B₂)
230 standards available.

231 Several studies have assessed the variations in total FOS in fructan-containing plants
232 stored at different temperatures (Ishiguro, Onodera, Benkeblia and Shiomi, 2010).
233 However, here the individual concentrations of the five FOS analysis was determined in
234 table grapes by HPAEC-PAD and their changes quantified in response to low
235 temperature (0 °C) and high CO₂ pretreatment (20% CO₂ for 3 days). In the HPAEC-
236 PAD chromatograms (Fig. 2) the 1-kestose (3a) and neokestose (3b) profiles detected in
237 non-treated (Fig. 2A) and CO₂-treated grapes (Fig. 2B) were identified. Accordingly, 1-
238 kestose was the predominant FOS, with an initial content of $10.11 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{g/g FW}$. The
239 amount of this FOS detected increased significantly to $17.00 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{g/g FW}$ following
240 exposure to high levels of CO₂ for 3 days (Fig. 2C), while in non-treated grapes no
241 significant increase was observed. The increase in 1-kestose content induced by high
242 CO₂ levels was also maintained when treated grapes were transferred to air, except for a
243 decrease observed on day 12. By contrast, the levels of neokestose remained at the
244 initial ($5.15 \pm 0.94 \mu\text{g/g FW}$) steady-state level in CO₂-treated and non-treated grapes
245 throughout the storage period (Fig. 2D).

246 The different behavior between 1-kestose and neokestose could reflect their different
247 biosynthesis pathways. While 1-kestose belongs to the inulin series of linked β -(1-2),
248 the first degree of lower FOS polymerization, neokestose belongs to the inulin neoseries
249 linked to β -(2-6). In 1-kestose synthesis, the 1-SST (sucrose:sucrose 1-
250 fructosyltransferase) enzyme initiates fructan synthesis by catalyzing the transfer of a

251 fructosyl residue from sucrose to another sucrose molecule. By contrast, the neokestose
252 of the inulin neoseries is synthesized in two steps. First, 1-SST produces 1-kestose and
253 then, 1-kestose is used as a donor substrate in the second step by the enzyme 6G-FFT
254 (6-glucose fructosyltransferase), which catalyses the transfer of a fructose residue of 1-
255 kestose to the carbon 6 of sucrose to form neokestose (Shiomi, 1981; Wiemken,
256 Sprenger & Boiler, 1995). Based on the present HPAEC-PAD results, we suggest that
257 CO₂-treated grapes produce inulin series FOS and therefore, the 1-kestose synthesized
258 is used for tetrasaccharide (nystose) formation, seldom serving as a substrate for
259 neokestose synthesis. Indeed, lower neokestose levels were detected in this study.

260 Figure 3 shows the HPAEC-PAD chromatographic profiles together with the zoom of
261 nystose (4c) and nystose b (4b) in non-treated (Fig. 3A) and CO₂-treated grapes (Fig.
262 3B). While the initial nystose levels ($0.93 \pm 0.35 \mu\text{g/g FW}$) (Fig. 3C) remained constant
263 in non-treated grapes, its content increased significantly and progressively in CO₂-
264 treated grapes during storage, mainly towards the end, reaching values of 3.26 ± 0.49
265 $\mu\text{g/g FW}$. By contrast, nystose b content (Fig. 3D) remained quite stable throughout
266 storage in both non-treated and CO₂-treated grapes. Although further work is needed to
267 define the mechanisms involved in FOS induction in CO₂-treated grapes, these results
268 are consistent with our suggestion that the inulin series FOS (1-kestose, nystose) rather
269 than FOS of other inulin neoseries (neokestose, nystose b) seem to be involved in FOS
270 accumulation.

271 Figure 4 shows the HPAEC-PAD chromatographic profiles together with the zoom of
272 kestopentaose (5a) in non-treated (Fig. 4A) and CO₂-treated grapes (Fig. 4B). The
273 evolution of kestopentaose (Fig. 4C) differed slightly from that of the other FOS.
274 Although an early rise in the levels of this FOS was evident after 3 day CO₂ treatment
275 however, the increase was only significant after 22 days at 0 °C, when the

276 pentasaccharide accumulation ($3.25 \pm 0.85 \mu\text{g/g FW}$) was twice that in non-treated
277 grapes. The levels of this FOS remained stable throughout the storage period in non-
278 treated grapes (Fig. 4C).

279 Although significant progress has been made in the analysis of fructan-accumulating
280 plants (Shiomi, Benkeblia & Onodera, 2007), to our knowledge this is the first time that
281 FOS have been characterized and quantified by HPAEC-PAD in the pulp of table
282 grapes. Furthermore, on analyzing the effect of different environmental conditions we
283 find that during postharvest storage at 0°C , CO_2 -treated grapes generate an immediate
284 response that induces the accumulation of FOS. It is also important to note the residual
285 effect of CO_2 -treatment on grapes during long-term storage at 0°C , indicating that CO_2 -
286 treatment could also affect the complex regulation of the enzymes involved in FOS
287 synthesis and depolymerisation.

288 There are many positive issues related to the presence of fructans in plants and indeed,
289 the synthesis of fructans confers resistance to the plant against several abiotic stresses
290 (Hincha, Zuther, Hellwege & Heyer 2002; Livingston et al., 2009). Hence, FOS might
291 provide protection from the damage to cytosolic proteins and cell membranes caused by
292 low temperature (Hoekstra, Golovina & Buitink, 2001), and they might act as
293 cryoprotectants (Van den Ende, Mintiens, Speleers, Onuoha & Van Laere, 1996).
294 Accordingly, the accumulation of FOS in CO_2 -treated berries, considering the
295 competitive advantage afforded by these grapes with less tissue disorganization and
296 reduced water leakage (Goñi, Fernandez-Caballero, Sanchez-Ballesta, Escribano, &
297 Merodio, 2011), raises questions suggesting that these water soluble compounds are
298 involved in some important functions. FOS accumulation during cold storage in CO_2 -
299 treated fruit may constitute an important metabolic response to protect cells from the
300 damage caused by storage at severe low temperatures in air. The use of high CO_2 levels

301 to enhance table grape quality has been reported previously (Retamales, Defilippi,
302 Arias, Castillo & Manríquez, 2003; Sanchez-Ballesta et al., 2006). Furthermore, the
303 beneficial effect of high CO₂ concentrations concurs with a decrease in the induction of
304 APX gene expression, suggesting a reduction in the stress imposed when compared to
305 non-treated grapes stored at 0 °C (Romero et al., 2008). Further experiments will be
306 necessary to investigate the activity of purified FOS-metabolizing enzymes, and to
307 understand the mechanism regulating their synthesis and depolymerization in Cardinal
308 table grapes. Such information should help clarify their physiological roles in FOS
309 metabolism, and how they are induced by CO₂-treatment during cold storage.

310 In conclusion, this study demonstrate that small amounts of FOS, as yet undetected, are
311 permanent components in freshly harvested Cardinal table grapes, and that they are
312 environmentally regulated. Moreover, high CO₂ treatment during low temperature
313 storage affects the quantity and distribution of FOS. Our results suggest that by
314 increasing the concentrations and the timing of FOS accumulation, beneficial CO₂
315 treatment could prevent the structural damage caused by storage at suboptimal low
316316 temperatures.

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417417 **Figure Captions**

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419 **Figure 1:** HPAEC-PAD chromatograms of FOS extracted from pulp berries with (A)
420 and without (B) activated carbon pre-treatment. The identified FOS in the sample (A₁)
421 was confirmed spiking with standard 1-kestose (**3a**) (A₂). The sample (B₁) was spiked
422 with standard nystose (**4c**) and kestopentaose (**5a**) (B₂).

423 **Figure 2:** HPAEC-PAD chromatography profile of 1-kestose (**3a**) and neokestose (**3b**)
424 in the pulp of non-treated (A) and CO₂-treated (B) table grapes. The 1-kestose was
425 quantified from the peak area using 1-kestose as standard. Changes in 1-kestose (C) and
426 neokestose (D) levels of non-treated and CO₂-treated table grapes during storage at 0
427 °C. The data are presented as the means ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the different
428 letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$). An asterisk * indicates a significant
429 effect of the CO₂ treatment.

430 **Figure 3:** HPAEC-PAD chromatography profile of nystose in non-treated (A) and CO₂-
431 treated (B) table grapes. Nystose was quantified from the peak area using nystose as
432 standard. Changes in the levels in nystose (**4c**) (C) and nystose b (**4b**) (D) in non-treated
433 and CO₂-treated table grapes during storage at 0 °C. Data are presented as the means ±
434 SE of three replicates (n=6). The different letters indicate significant differences
435 ($p<0.05$).

436 **Figure 4:** HPAEC-PAD chromatography profile of kestopentaose (**5a**) concentrations
437 in non-treated (A) and CO₂-treated (B) table grapes. Kestopentaose was quantified from
438 the peak area using kestopentaose as standard. Changes in the levels of kestopentaose
439 (**5a**) (C) in non-treated and CO₂-treated table grapes during storage at 0 °C. The data are
440 presented as the means ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the different letters indicate

441 significant differences ($p < 0.05$). An asterisk * indicates a significant effect of CO₂
442442 treatment.
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Table 1. Changes in glucose, fructose, and sucrose levels (mg/g FW) in the pulp of non-treated and CO₂-treated table grapes during storage at 0 °C.

Days	glucose		fructose		sucrose	
	non-treated	CO ₂ -treated	non-treated	CO ₂ -treated	non-treated	CO ₂ -treated
0	100.40±0.48	100.40±0.48	94.78±0.86	94.78±0.86	5.71±0.55	5.71±0.55
3	102.61±6.57	110.88±3.26	99.55±6.63	105.84±3.37	5.39±0.34	4.68±0.03
6	113.24±3.89	94.00±3.54	108.15±3.26	89.71±4.86	7.32±0.62	4.21±0.38
12	96.61±11.29	98.27±5.87	93.77±10.99	95.79±5.44	5.88±0.65	6.09±0.75
22	92.76±5.51	89.30±6.86	90.56±6.27	91.05±8.13	6.09±0.44	4.89±0.34
Significance ^y	D*, DxT*		D*, DxT*		D*,T*,DxT*	

Data are presented as the means ± SE of three replicates (n=6).

^y Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ using Bonferroni's test, where D = days and T = CO₂ treatment.

Figure 1
Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 4

Figure 4

C

Fructo-oligosaccharides (FOS) are permanent components in table grapes

Individual concentrations of the five FOS by HPAEC-PAD analysis

1-kestose and kestopentaose accumulation in response to high CO₂ levels

High CO₂ treatment affects the quantity and distribution of FOS

FOS are environmentally regulated